

EVALUATION OF PEPTIC ULCER PERCEPTION AND PREVENTION STRATEGIES CIVIL SERVANTS ASSESSING HEALTHCARE SERVICES AT THE NIGER UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL, OKOLOBIRI IN YENAGOA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: *This study Evaluation Peptic ulcer perception and prevention strategies among male and female civil servants assessing healthcare services in the Niger Delta University teaching hospital okolobiri, Yenagoa Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A total of 760; 48.82 % male and 51.18% female respondents were randomly selected for the study. A well-structured and validated questionnaire was used to collect information on the sociodemographic, economic, perception and prevention strategies of peptic ulcer. Data collected was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and results were presented in frequency and percentage.*

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The results revealed that the respondents age range to be within the range of 36 to 4 years old – male 56.15 % and female 61.08%. There monthly income was above 100k with 25 % of the male respondents 25% earning more than 350 k monthly. Majority of the respondents had a first degree with similar percentages of higher degree. Food and drug intake analysis shows that 54% of the female respondents skipped meals as compared to the male 39 .4% the meals often skipped by both respondents was Breakfast. Majority of the respondents ate breakfast at home 59.3 % female and 59.4 male. Alcohol intake was higher in the females 57.5 % respondents compared to male 47.7%. Result of the peptic ulcer perception and prevention strategies among the respondents' shows that both male and female respondents had a good knowledge of the cause and prevention strategies in Peptic ulcer. They indicated drug abuse, meals skipping, and alcohol intake as a risk factor for peptic ulcer.

Beans porridge and plantain pepper soup ranked highest among the Foods they avoid due to peptic ulcer. Food selection topped highest as a means of prevention peptic use male 87.3 % and female 79.69%. Majority of the respondents male 64.4% and female 51.9 % indicated Coke as a brand of drink they avoid due to peptic ulcer. Drug abuse ranked highest 28% by male respondents followed by meal skipping among the factor that aggravates symptoms, while the female respondents indicated alcohol 34.4% and drug abuse 21.1 6%. Therefore, interventions should be tailored towards good dietary practices, behavioral changes that improve good Life style choice to reduce the prevalence of Peptic ulcer disease among civil servants.

Introduction

Ulcer diseases refer to a group of medical conditions characterized by the development of open sores or ulcers on the mucous membranes or skin (Narayanan, *et al.*, 2018). These ulcers can occur in various parts of the digestive system, but they most commonly develop in the stomach (gastric ulcers) or the upper part of the small intestine called the duodenum (duodenal ulcers). Ulcer remains a significant healthcare concern, particularly among individuals with limited mobility and those confined to healthcare

facilities. These painful and potentially life-threatening wounds can lead to prolonged hospital stays, increased healthcare costs, and diminished quality of life for affected patients (Tschannen-Moran, *et al.*, 2016). While Peptic ulcers duodenal are largely preventable, healthcare workers and Civil servants in Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri Yenegoa, Bayelsa State play a critical role in their prevention and management.

Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is characterized by discontinuation in the inner lining of the

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gastrointestinal (GI) tract because of gastric acid secretion or pepsin (Tschannen-Moran, *et al.*, 2016). It extends into the muscularis propria layer of the gastric epithelium. It usually occurs in the stomach and proximal duodenum. It may involve the lower esophagus, distal duodenum, or jejunum. Epigastric pain usually occurs within 15-30 minutes following a meal in patients with a gastric ulcer; on the other hand, the pain with a duodenal ulcer tends to occur 2-3 hours after a meal. Today, testing for *Helicobacter pylori* is recommended in all patients with peptic ulcer disease. Endoscopy may be required in some patients to confirm the diagnosis, especially in those patients with sinister symptoms. Today, most patients can be managed with a proton pump inhibitor (PPI) based triple-drug therapy (Narayanan, *et al.*, 2018). The importance of healthcare workers and civil servants understanding, perception, and implementation of ulcer prevention strategies cannot be overstated. These professionals are at the forefront of patient care and smooth running of state affairs and are responsible for identifying and mitigating risk factors, regularly repositioning patients, and maintaining adequate skin hygiene. Their knowledge and adherence to evidence-based prevention strategies are pivotal in reducing the incidence of ulcers (Lanas, *et al.*, 2015).

Ulcers, particularly peptic ulcers, are common gastrointestinal disorders that affect millions of people worldwide. These painful sores, typically found in the stomach or the duodenum, can lead

to various complications if left untreated, including bleeding, perforation, and in some cases, cancer (Ferguson, *et al.*, 2015). The pathophysiology of ulcers is multifactorial, involving the interplay of factors such as *Helicobacter pylori* infection, non-steroidal antiinflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) usage, and lifestyle factors like stress and smoking (Ferguson, *et al.*, 2015).

This study aims to assess the perception and implementation of ulcer prevention strategies among male and female civil servants assessing care services in Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri Yenegoa, Bayelsa State. By addressing the gaps in knowledge and practices, this research endeavors to contribute to the overall improvement of patient care and outcomes, reduce healthcare costs, and advance the field of peptic ulcer prevention in healthcare settings.

Ulcers, particularly peptic/duodenal ulcers, pose a significant healthcare challenge worldwide, affecting patients' quality of life and healthcare costs. Peptic Ulcer disease prevalence in South Nigeria is 6.7%, this overall rate is in line with global prevalence trend of 5-10% for PUD. (Nwokediuko, *et al.*, 2017). Civil servants play crucial roles in nation building care and are potential sources of information and implementation of ulcer perception and prevention strategies (Tschannen-Moran, *et al.*, 2016). However, there is a pressing need to evaluate their awareness, understanding, and adherence to these strategies.

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This study will improve peptic ulcer/duodenal care knowledge and prevention among civil servants assessing healthcare services in Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri Yenegoa, Bayelsa State by providing insights into how well these groups understand the risks associated with peptic ulcers and how they can prevent them. This knowledge can potentially lead to improved patient care in healthcare facilities and better health outcomes for civil servants.

Literature Review

Ulcers are a significant healthcare concern worldwide. Ulcers not only result in patient suffering but also impose a considerable economic burden on healthcare systems. In order to effectively combat this issue, it is crucial to evaluate the perception of ulcers and the preventive strategies among health workers and civil servants, (Hunt & Xiao, 2014). This literature review aims to explore the current state of knowledge on this topic, shedding light on the understanding, awareness, and implementation of ulcer prevention strategies within these two distinct groups.

According to Kelanne and Emeka, (2020), Peptic ulcer is a disease of antiquity with the first medical report in the 14th century B.C. it is a breach in gastric or duodenal epithelium extremely beyond the muscular mucosal protective factors. Medplus (2023), also define peptic ulcer as a break in skin or mucous membrane with loss of surface tissue, disintegration and necroses of epithelial issue,

and often pus. Peptic ulcer disease is characterized by discontinuation in the inner lining of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT): because of gastric acid secretion of pepsin, it extends into the muscularis propria layer of the gastric epithelium, occurring in the oesophagus, distal duodenum or jejunum.

Helicobacter pylori belongs to the family *Helicobacteraceae*. It is a transmissible and pathogenic gram-negative spiral-shaped bacterium thought to be a contaminant of digested food as opposed to being a true colonizer of the gastric mucosa (Kusters, *et al.*, 2015). It was first successfully isolated and discovered by Barry Marshall and Robin Warren in 1980, for which they were awarded the Nobel Prize in 2005 (Morris & Nicholson, 2012). They intentionally ingested the bacterium and subsequently developed persistent gastritis. Later, it was found that the bacteria are strongly associated with multiple upper gastrointestinal disorders, such as chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, gastric mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma, and gastric cancer (Fock, *et al.*, 2013).

H. pylori is the most common human bacterial infection occurring in 4.4 billion people, representing over 50% of the world population. The World Health Organization (WHO) now considers it a class 1 carcinogen leading to peptic ulcer disease and gastric cancer (Burkitt, *et al.*, 2017). The *H. pylori* infection rate is 30–50% in developed and 85–95% in developing countries (Bauer, *et al.*, 2012). More specifically, the

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infection rate is 30% in Western countries and 20–30% in North America, in which it is 23% in the province of Ontario and 13% in Quebec. Infection rates are higher in Africans (25%), Asians (30%), and South Americans (34%) and significantly lower in Caucasians (8%) who reside in Canada (Wroblewski, *et al.*, 2010). The pathogen is more prevalent in North Americans, Aboriginals, and recent immigrants (Bravo, *et al.*, 2018).

In 2006, the Canadian North Helicobacter pylori Working Group were established to identify specifically the impact of H. pylori infection in the Canadian Arctic communities (Alexander, *et al.*, 2021). The rate of documented infection in these communities was 55% in the 2008 survey. In one study, 95% seropositivity was revealed in the native community in northwestern Manitoba

and a 67% infection rate in children two years of age. The pathogen is also prevalent in Aboriginals of Russia, Alaska, and Greenland, and the infection ratio ranged from 47% to 88%, (Burucoa & Axon, 2017). Furthermore, the infection rate is relatively higher in immigrants from countries such as India or China than in those born in Canada from the same ethnic groups (World Gastroenterology Organization, (WGO) (2011)).

H. pylori infection prevalence increases with age within the first ten years of life (Hunt, *et al.*, 2011). The incidence of H. pylori infection in childhood varies greatly. The childhood infection rate in some underdeveloped countries is reported to be 90% (Willems, *et al.*, 2020) while in developed countries, it ranges from as low as 1.8% to as high as 65%.

Category	Prevalence
Infected people	4.4 billion (by 2015)
Developing countries	50.8%
Developed countries	34.7%
H. pylori rate in females	42.7%
H. pylori rate in males	46.3%
H. pylori rate in children	32.6%
Africa	70.1%
South Asia (Pakistan)	81.0%
South Asia (India)	63.5%
Western Asia	77.2%
North America	20%–30%

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United States of America	30%–40%
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Sources: Naja, Kreiger, & Sullivan (2017); Goodman, Jacobson, & Veldhuyzen van Zanten (2018); Jones, Chiba, Fallone et al., (2012), Cheung, Goodman, & Munday, et al. (2018)

The exact mechanism of *H. pylori* infection is currently unknown; however, socioeconomic and environmental factors are known to play an important role (Johansen, *et al.*, 2014). *H. pylori* infection occurs in early childhood and remains silent for years; only 30% of individuals develop observable signs and symptoms of gastritis. Transmission occurs through oral-oral, fecal-oral, and gastro-oral routes (Reshetnikov, *et al.*, 2017). As an example, mother-to-child transmission occurs if the mother's saliva is contaminated or due to poor hand hygiene. The pathogen is transmitted by direct means, e.g., kissing or sharing utensils, or by indirect means, such as drinking water, air, animals, flies, and food.

The occurrence of *H. pylori* infection supports the transmission of fecal contaminants in the institutionalized young population during the epidemic of gastroenteritis (Zhu, *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, in refrigerated food, the pathogen may survive for a short period and is the source of infection (Younger & Duggan, 2012). Additionally, it is associated with dietary habits, particularly milk, meat, and vegetables (Bateson,

2010). One Indian study revealed that the prevalence is more common in the lower socioeconomic group (Tiwari, *et al.*, 2018). Drinking unfiltered water, tobacco, and meat consumption are risk factors for developing *H. pylori* infection. Moreover, drinking unboiled water in restaurants in urban areas increases the spread of the pathogen (Mahalanabis, *et al.*, 2019). The acquisition and transmission of the pathogen increase in dense living conditions, when using non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, in the blood group O, with obesity, and with a family history of gastric disease (Salih, 2016). Eating fried food has a positive correlation with infection.

Antibiotic resistance is another contributing factor for *H. pylori* infection as antibiotic resistance is primarily responsible for failing to completely eradicate *H. pylori*. In certain cases, a patient will undergo 14 days of quadruple therapy and, subsequently, either develop the infection again or develop complications of *H. pylori* infection. The main cause of antibiotic resistance is the overuse of antibiotics; metronidazole shows the highest resistance rate and is widely used in most countries for various gastrointestinal illnesses (Hestvik, *et al.*, 2010). A major contributor to the increased prevalence of bacterial infections, including *H. pylori* infection, is the global emergence of antibiotic-

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resistant bacteria, threatening the efficacy of antibiotics which have transformed medicine and saved countless lives (Roma & Miele, 2015). The leading cause of antibiotic resistance is the overuse or misuse of antibiotics due to a misguided perception in many people that antibiotics can cure any kind of illness. This has caused people to view antibiotics as a cure-all and routinely request them from their physicians, even for viral illnesses. This, compounded with the improper use of antibiotics, leads to resistance.

Additionally, incorrectly prescribed antibiotics also promote antibiotic resistance. Research reveals that in 30–50% of cases, the indication for treatment, antibiotic choice, and duration of antibiotic therapy is incorrect (Malaty *et al.*, 2016). In many countries, antibiotics are available over the counter without prescription; this ease of obtaining antibiotics also contributes to the problem (Hooi, *et al.*, 2017). Lack of regulation and easy availability of a variety of cheap antibiotics in the market as well as online lead to the misuse and overuse of antibiotics (Zamani *et al.*, 2018).

Finally, the lack of new drug development by the pharmaceutical industry due to the decreased financial incentives and challenging regulatory requirements is contributing to the antibiotic resistance crisis (Kayali *et al.*, 2018). New research policies and coordinated efforts to control antibiotic resistance are greatly needed.

This will help in the eradication of bacterial pathogens.

Perception of Peptic Ulcers

i. Awareness among Health Workers
Healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, play a vital role in ulcer prevention and management. Various studies have indicated that while healthcare workers are generally knowledgeable about peptic ulcers, there are gaps in their awareness and understanding of specific risk factors and preventive measures (Beekman *et al.*, 2019). These gaps may lead to suboptimal care and increased ulcer incidence.

ii. Among Civil Servants in contrast to healthcare workers, civil servants often have limited exposure to ulcer-related knowledge and may underestimate the importance of prevention. This lack of awareness can hinder their ability to recognize early signs of ulcers in themselves or their colleagues, leading to delayed intervention (Polit & Beck, 2017).

Materials and Method

Study Area

The Study Area is the Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri Yenegoa, Bayelsa State. The Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital (NDUTH) - The hospital was established in 1982 as a cottage hospital located at Okolobiri, a community in Gbarain-Ekpetiama in Yenegoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State and then upgraded to the status of a teaching Hospital in September 2007, as part of the states' developmental agenda. The

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upgrading was implemented by the military administrator, Group Captain Phillip Ayeni in 1996. With the establishment of the Niger Delta University and the College of Health Sciences in Bayelsa State, there was the urgent need to train medical students, house officers, nurses and students from other paramedical disciplines.

The Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital (NDUTH) is the only tertiary teaching hospital in Bayelsa state, the core of the Niger Delta Region in Nigeria. We offer tertiary health services, train healthcare manpower and conduct health research for the good of humanity. The vision is to provide Excellent Healthcare in line with International Best Practices in an environment that is suitable for training of highly skilled Healthcare Professionals as well as conducting productive health research for the good of humanity in collaboration with other bodies - institutions. The hospital is a 150-bed hospital.

Study Design

A cross sectional design will be adopted in this study. Civil servants assessing healthcare at the Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital Okolobiri Yenegoa, Bayelsa State will be randomly selected within the study period March 2024 to December, 2024.

Study Population

Male and female Civil servants assessing healthcare services in Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital Okolobiri Yenegoa, Bayelsa State whose grade level is from 7 upwards will be the target population of this study.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size for the study will be determined from the population of civil servants assessing healthcare in the hospital during the study period. Yamane formula will be used to get the sample size.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n = required sample size

N = 8,100 (Population of male and female civil servants) e = desired margin of error (10% margin of error)

$$n = \frac{8,100}{1 + 8,100 (0.05)^2}$$

Now, calculate the sample size:

$$n = \frac{8,100}{1 + 8,100 (0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{8,100}{11.25}$$

n = 704

Adding attrition rate of 10% = 0.10 x 704 = 70

Therefore, Sample size (s) = 704 + 70

= 774 ÷ 2

= 387 male and 387 female

Sampling Technique

Civil servants who agreed to participate in the study were recruited using simple random sampling technique. The respondents were male and female civil servants with grade level 17 assessing healthcare services at Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital who registered with Bayelsa health Insurance scheme.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria: Civil servants registered under the BHIS scheme within ages of 18 to 60 assessing healthcare services in Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital whose grade level is from 7 and above were eligible and included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Civil servants assessing healthcare in Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital whose grade level is below 7 were not eligible and excluded from the study.

Consent

Informed consent was obtained from each respondent after a detailed explanation of what the study entails and strict confidentiality was observed.

Validation of the Method of Study

A structured questionnaire to collect information on the socio-demographic, economic, knowledge, and perception of peptic ulcer, prevention and management validated by lecturers in the department of Nutrition and Dietetics, Imo State University was used for the study.

Data Collection Method

Structured validated questionnaire was used to collect data for the project.

Data Analysis

The data collected was analysed using the statistical package for the social science (SPSS)

and results presented descriptively in table, frequency and percentages. Chi square test (χ^2) was used to complete the means response in the population at % ($p \leq 0.05$) 5% confidence level.

Results

Results in table 1 shows the number of male and female respondents that participated in the study. 371 males and 389 females total of 760 respondents (48.82%) male 51.18% female. The table revealed a higher percentage of the respondents were within the age group of (36 – 40) range male 29.40%, female 30.33% followed by 41-45 age range male 20.75% and female. 30.75% the educational level of the male respondents revealed 46.1% of men had B.Sc/HND/1st degree while that of female was 47.6%. the percentage of male that had higher degree M.Sc/PHD was almost similar to those of the female male 16.4% female 16%. It was revealed from the result 25% of female respondents earn higher monthly income compared to the male respondents. Higher percentage 49% of the spouse of the female respondents earned above 350,000 naira compared to those of the male respondents who earned above than 350,000 naira was 33%, majority of the respondents earned more than 200,000 naira monthly.

Table 1: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Variable	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Sex				
Male	371			
Female	389			
Age (years)				
18-24	4	1.0	7	1.8
25-30	28	7.6	14	4.0
31-35	49	13.20	43	11.0
36-40	79	21.30	69	17.7
41-45	109	29.40	118	30.33
46-50	77	20.75	117	30.1
51 and above	25	6.73	20	5.14
	371	100	389	100.0
Occupation				
Public/civil servant	371	100	389	100.0
Educational level				
Primary	33	8.92	13	3.3
JSS	31	8.36	20	5.1
SSCE	35	9.46	46	11.8
OND/NCE	39	10.52	67	17.2
HND/BSC/BA	171	46.1	185	47.6
MSC	52	14.02	27	7
PHD	10	2.62	31	8
	371	100	389	100

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Average monthly income (₦)

<100,000	88	23.7	90	23.3
100,000-150,000	98	26.42	60	15.5
151,000-200,000	80	21.57	91	23.3
251,000-300,000	34	9.17	33	8.4
301,000 -400,000	14	3.78	29	7.5
401,000 and above	57	15.36	82	21
	371	100	389	100

Partners age (years)

<25	51	13.74	41	10.5
25-30years	59	15.9	62	15.9
31-35	59	15.9	66	17.0
36-40	57	15.37	91	23.4
41-50	70	18.87	43	11.1
51 and above	75	20.22	25	6.4
	371	100	389	100.0

Partners educational level

Primary	7	1.91	9	2.3
JSS	9	2.46	36	9.3
SSCE	21	5.64	47	12.1
OND/NCE	66	17.72	41	10.5
HND/BSC/BA	102	27.51	155	39.8
MSC	79	21.3	91	23.4
PHD	87	23.46	10	2.6
	371	100	389	100.0

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Partners income	monthly			
<100,000	43	11.59	36	9.3
100,000-150,000	81	21.84	51	13.3
151,000-200,000	71	19.13	58	15.2
251,000-300,000	43	11.59	27	7
301,000-351,000	9	2.43	20	5.2
351,000 and above	124	33.42	183	49
	371	100	389	100.0
TOTAL	371	100	389	100.0

The result in table 2 shows that 66% of male respondents ate breakfast before leaving home while 61% of the female ate before leaving home. Breakfast was eaten at home by 59.3% of the male respondent and that of the female was 59.4%. Breakfast was eaten at the office by 27.8% of the male respondents and 18.7% of the female respondents. The results revealed 72.5% of the male respondents skipped meals 4 times weekly as compared to the female respondents that was 65.8%, meal skipping pattern was high in both the male and female respondents. The percentage of female who skipped breakfast 53.2% was higher compared to that of the male

39.4%. Breakfast meal 57.5% was the most skipped meal among the male and female respondents compared to lunch and dinner.

The female respondents had higher intake of alcohol 52.3% compared to the male 47.7% followed by intake of pain killers 31.5% in male and 27% in female. Intake of cigarette was low among the male and female respondents 4% in male and 2.5% in female respectively. Frequency of intake of painkillers was low less than 5 times in the last one month was 39.1% in male and 42.4% in female, followed by 24.80% above 14 times in male and 20.8% in female respondents.

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Table 2 FOOD AND DRUG INTAKE HABIT OF THE RESPONDENTS

Variable	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Eating before leaving home in the morning				
Always	104	28.0	87	22.4
Most times	141	38.0	149	38.3
Not regular	81	21.83	103	26.5
Hardly	45	12.12	50	12.9
	371	100	389	100
Breakfast is mostly eaten at				
Office	103	27.8	73	18.7
Home	220	59.3	231	59.4
Street food vendors	15	4.0	50	12.9
Fast food	21	5.7	28	7.2
Traffic	12	3.2	7	1.8
	371	100	389	100
Meal skipping Pattern				
4 times in a weekly	269	72.5	256	65.8
3 times weekly	72	19.4	91	23.4
2 times weekly	27	7.3	32	8.2
Once in a week	3	0.8	10	2.6
	371	100	389	100
Meal usually skipped				
Breakfast	146	39.4	207	53.2
Lunch	122	32.9	89	23.3
Dinner	18	4.9	18	4.6
None	85	22.8	60	15.5
	371	100	389	100
Substance often taken				
Painkillers	116	31.3	105	27.0

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Cigarette	15	4.0	10	2.5
Alcohol	177	47.7	223	57.3
Paractenes/ Panadol	63	16.98	51	13.11
	371	100	389	100
frequency of substance consumption in the last month				
>5times	145	39.1	165	42.4
5-7times	76	20.5	75	19.3
8-10times	40	4.8	43	11.1
11-14times	18	23.2	22	5.7
14 time and above	92	1.6	81	20.8
Total	371	100	389	100

Table 3 results of the study indicated that 40.4% of the male respondents understood the concept of peptic ulcer and responded correctly to the meaning of peptic ulcer. 23% of the female respondents correctly, majority above 50% of the male and female responded correctly to the signs and symptoms of peptic ulcer, about 85.54% of the male respondents have heard of the word peptic ulcer while 85.45% of the female respondents affirm likewise. Source of peptic ulcer information was 37.46% from doctors, 19.13% from social media; source of peptic information from female respondents was 38.8% doctors 30.1% from friends.

The knowledge about types of ulcer were high for gastric ulcer with female respondents 88.9% and male 39.1% peptic ulcer men 18.9% female 0.8%. A higher percentage of the male respondents seems to be more aware of the different types of

ulcer compared to the female about 70.35% of the male respondents indicated they were suspected to have peptic ulcer while the female was 80.98% Results shows that 40.9% of male had peptic ulcer, 28.3% stomach ulcer among the female respondents it was revealed that 34.44% had peptic ulcer and 50.64% had stomach ulcer. Meal skipped ranked highest in the knowledge about the causes of peptic ulcer in male and female respondents 54.5% female and 32 – 61% male. Knowledge of peptic ulcer treatment by medication was higher in both the male and female respondent as compared to other methods of treatments like herbal, 13.5% male 13.4% female. Majority of the male respondents 87.33% and female 79.6% indicated that food selection plays a role in peptic ulcer treatment. The result shows that 54.5% of the female and 29.64% of male respondents indicated that avoiding

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drug abuse is a way of preventing peptic ulcer. The result further indicated that 86.79% male and 84.54 respondents had seen and known persons that have been affected by peptic ulcer. About 41.23% of male respondents indicated that acidic foods trigger peptic ulcer while 40.70% affirms peppery food triggers it; while it was 68.4% and 7.7% amongst the female respondents.

More than one third 31% of the male respondents indicated beans porridge and plantain pepper soup 35.6% as food they now avoid due to peptic ulcer, it was 31.1% and 46.3% among female respondents.

Majority of the female respondents 64.4% and female 51.9% indicated coke as the drink they

mostly avoided due to peptic ulcer followed by cigarettes and drug abuse, only 0.8% male and 10% female respondents indicated alcohol avoidance.

Drug abuse ranked highest 28% followed by sleep deprivation among factors that aggravates the symptoms of ulcer among the male respondents while alcohol ranked highest among female respondents 34.4% followed by drug abuse 22.1%. Avoidance of alcoholic ranked highest 64.4% among the actions that should be taken to prevent reoccurrence of peptic ulcer amongst the male respondents, followed by Cigarette avoidance 65.3% among the female respondents

Table 3: PEPTIC ULCER PERCEPTION AND PREVENTION STRATEGIES OF THE RESPONDENTS

Variable	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Meaning of ulcer				
Gas filled with stomach	90	24.5	90	23.1
All day long pain in the stomach	150	40.4	74	19.0
Burning sensation in throat	30	8	54	13.9
Pain in the stomach before eating only	52	14	120	30.8
During eating only	11	2.9	6	1.6
After eating only	38	10.2	45	11.6
	371	100	389	100.0

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Heard of ulcer before

Yes	329	88.7	332	85.34
No	42	11.3	57	14.65
	371	100	389	100.0

Place you heard about Ulcer and believed

Media	31	8.4	31	8.0
Partner	39	10.4	44	11.3
Parents in-law	15	4.0	10	2.6
Friends	25	6.7	117	30.1
Doctor	139	37.46	151	38.8
Social media	71	19.13	15	3.9
Dietitian	51	13.74	21	5.4
	371	100	389	100.0

Types of ulcer you know

Gastric	145	39.1	346	88.9
Duodenal	52	14.01	17	4.4
Mouth	37	9.97	17	4.4
Peptic ulcer	70	18.9	3	.8
Others	67	18.05	6	1.5
	371	100	389	100.0

Have you been suspected/treated of ulcer before

Yes	261	70.35	315	80.98
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No	110	29.65	74	19.02
	371	100	389	100

Type of ulcer you have

Stomach	105	28.3	197	50.64
Gastric/ duodenal	104	28.1	44	11.31
Mouth ulcers	10	2.7	14	3.59
Peptic ulcer	152	40.9	134	34.44
	371	100	389	100.0

Seen or known anyone affected by ulcer

Yes	322	86.79	329	84.58
No	49	13.21	60	15.42
	371	100	389	100.0

Type of ulcer the person had

Stomach ulcer	69	18.59	164	42.2
Gastric ulcer	106	28.6	25	6.4
Duodenal	27	7.28	35	9
Peptic ulcer	169	45.55	165	42.4
	371	100	389	100.0

Relationship with the person

Father	41	11.05	126	32.4
Mother	71	19.13	248	63.8
Brother	41	11.05	3	.8

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Sister	45	12.12	3	.8
Friend	146	39.35	6	1.5
Others	27	7.27	3	.8
	371	100	389	100

Duration of the disease to the person

<1year	102	27.49	106	27.2
1-2years	85	22.91	45	11.6
3-4years	112	30.18	113	29.04
4-5years	24	6.46	13	3.3
5years and above	48	12.93	112	28.9
	371	100	389	100

Factors that causes ulcer

Meal skipping	121	32.61	212	54.5
Over eating	3	0.8	58	14.9
Germs infection	75	20.21	9	2.3
Dry fasting	43	11.59	6	1.5
Sugary foods	18	4.85	9	2.3
Alcohol	64	17.25	64	16.5
Smoking	47	12.66	31	8.0
	371	100	389	100

How was the ulcer treated

Drug	211	56.87	280	79.97
Herbal	50	13.5	52	13.4

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Prayers	15	4.04	11	2.8
Nothing	15	4.04	4	1.0
Eat often	42	11.32	3	0.8
Exercise	38	10.24	39	10.02
	371	100	389	100

Actions taken to prevent ulcer

Medications	110	29.64	212	54.5
Herb	50	13.47	58	14.9
Avoid smoking	61	16.44	9	2.3
alcohol	50	13.47	37	9.5
Visit Pharmacy/Chemist	70	18.9	16	4.1
Consult nutritionist/ dietitians	30	8.1	64	16.5
	371	100	389	100

Thought that food selection help to treat ulcer

Yes	324	87.33	310	79.69
No	47	12.66	79	20.31
	371	100	389	100

Warning sign of ulcer

Hunger	27	7.27	12	3.1
Sudden urge to urinate	20	5.4	33	8.5
Diarrhea	15	4.4	36	9.3
Sharp pain in the throat	14	3.7	17	4.4

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Sharp pain in the heart	63	16.9	208	53.5
Biting stomach pain	232	62.5	83	21.3
	371	100	389	100

Types of food that can trigger ulcer

Sweet foods	12	3.32	77	19.8
Acidic foods	153	41.23	266	68.4
Peppery foods	151	40.70	30	7.7
Hot foods	55	14.82	16	4.11
	371	100	389	100

Food that can suppress ulcer

Sugar foods	55	14.82	105	27.0
Alkaline food	62	16.71	177	45.5
Acidic food	182	49.05	25	6.4
Hot foods	72	19.40	82	21.1
	371	100	389	100

Awareness that abuse of drugs causes ulcer

Yes	263	70.89	304	78.14
No	108	29.11	85	21.9
	371	100	389	100.0

Awareness that alcohol can cause ulcer

Yes	259	69.81	298	76.60
No	112	30.20	91	23.40
	371	100	389	100

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What food do you like but now must avoid due to ulcer

Eba and Egusi soup	3	.8	27	6.9
Rice and beans	30	8.1	121	31.1
Beans porridge	115	31.0	180	46.3
Unripe plantain (boiled with peper soup)	132	35.6	10	2.6
Fufu and okra soup	3	.8	35	9.0
Eba and Banga soup	37	10.0	7	1.8
Others	51	13.7	9	2.3
	371	100	389	100

What drink do you like but now must avoid due to ulcer

Coke	239	64.4	202	51.9
Malt drink	59	15.9	51	13.1
Energy drink	19	5.1	38	9.8
Alcoholic drink	3	0.8	39	10.0
Fanta	3	0.8	43	11.1
Others	48	12.9	16	4.1
	371	100	389	100

Lifestyle practice that can aggravate the symptom of ulcer

Physical exercise	62	16.17	32	8.2
Sleeplessness/sleep deprivation	72	19.40	43	11.1

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Drug abuse	105	28.30	86	22.1
Alcoholism	41	11.05	134	34.4
smoking	61	16.44	38	9.8
Stress	30	8.08	56	14.4
Total	371	100	389	100

What type of action should be taken to avoid reoccurrence of peptic ulcer in a patient

Avoid alcohol	239	64.4	64	16.5
Avoid smoking cigarette	59	15.9	254	65.3
Eat healthy	19	5.1	15	3.8
Manage stress	3	0.8	46	11.8
Avoid drug abuse	51	13.7	10	2.5
Total	371	100	389	100

Discussion

This study investigated the perception and prevention strategies of Peptic Ulcer Among female and male civil servants assessing healthcare services in the Niger Delta University teaching hospital okolobiri. Higher proportion of the respondents were female, the average age of the respondents was 45.2 which reflects a young population of civil servants in the state work force and awareness of risk factors of Peptic ulcer can help them prevent the disease and promote high productivity in the civil servants. The respondents in this study earned more than 200,000 naira which is in contrast with a study

by Alazvri where the respondents were low income earners this could be they the respondents in this study are senior civil servants and had multiple sources of income.

From the study, it was observed that higher proportion of the respondents were females. This was in contrary with the reports by Mohammed *et al.*, (2018). The result in this study was not similar to the reports by Alazvari (2022). Higher proportion of the respondents has HND/BSc/BA qualification; this contributes to the reason that they are all civil servants gainfully employed by government with their educational qualification. Previous studies (Poda *et al.*, 2019) have

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reported significant effect of income on the health status and nutritional status of individuals. Education has been seen to increase the knowledge and attitude of individuals towards health. Well educated individual has been seen to take maximum care of their health. From Table 2 Higher proportion of the respondents ate at home before leaving. This could be attributed to the fact that they are married and live with their partner who prepares meals for them. The finding in this study was consistent with the findings of Dafalla *et al.*, (2021). Majority of the respondents skipped meal, this could be attributed to the fact that most of the respondent's rush to work early in the morning, skipping meals and taking the meals to work mostly breakfast. The finding in this study was not consistent with the report of Nehling (2022). This study revealed a high record of alcohol intake among the female respondents compared to the male. This calls for concern and requires attention as excessive alcohol intake can cause complications in Peptic ulcer. Higher proportions of the respondents consume alcohol. Alcohol consumption has been seen to have negative effect on the health status of individuals. Alcohol increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases, obesity and overweight (Elsayd, 2018).

From table 3, higher proportion of the respondents believed that ulcer is an all-day pain in the stomach. This could be attributed to the fact that the respondents attending health care

services and are not professionals in health. Majority have heard about ulcer this showed that the respondents are assessing health care services and are being diagnosed of ulcers by the health care professionals. The findings in this study were similar to the reports by Albaequi *et al.*, (2019). Most of the respondents heard about ulcer from Doctors/ Nurses and Dietitians. This is in correspondences to the fact that they are being attended by Doctor/Nurses and dietitians during the health check-up. Higher proportion of the respondents believed that meal skipping causes ulcer. The findings in this study were similar to finding by Lanas (2017). Higher proportion of the respondents need that peppery foods cause's ulcer. The report in this study was contrary to the reports by Auang *et al.*, (2021). Previous reports that ulcer is caused by bacteria its pylori that weaken the mucosal livings of the stomach.

Conclusion

This study showed that most of the respondents male and female were within the age of 36 – 51 years and majority were first Degree (BSC/HND/BA) holders. They always eat from the home, majority skipped meal mostly breakfast and most of them take alcohol more than 5times in a month. Majority have heard about ulcer, and they opined that it was caused by consuming peppery foods and also alcohol consumption and drug abuse are risk factors of peptic ulcer. The respondents' perception on preventive strategies reveals a good health

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seeking behaviour and preventive practices, though there is still a gap on the effectiveness of current prevention strategy at the healthcare facility due to inadequate funding for staff training and preventive educational programme and implementation of occupational health policy for civil servant in the state. The importance of addressing peptic ulcer awareness among civil servants is crucial for many reasons which include work place productivity, risk reduction, mental health benefits, health promotion, public health impacts, policy development and empowerment. Thus, there is need for further study to access the long term

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effectiveness of some of the implemented strategies in the healthcare system

Recommendation

1) Based on the findings from the study, it is recommended that there is need to improve workplace health initiatives aimed at preventing peptic ulcer such as Nutrition education to enlighten the population on healthy dietary habits, lifestyle modification targeted to preventing and reducing the risk of peptic ulcer diseases.

2) Further study should be carried out to monitor changes in perception and prevention strategies over time.

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